

Exploration of Chatbots in Mathematics Education for Innovative Learning Process

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Authors CAP and DL designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. They managed the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aims: This study aimed to explore the potential of chatbots in mathematics education by introducing them as an innovative learning tool for Bachelor of Secondary Education Math students. Specifically, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how chatbots can be integrated into the mathematics learning process. Ultimately, this study aims to enhance the knowledge and understanding of chatbots' capabilities and their impact on educational environments, thereby contributing to improved educational outcomes in mathematics.

Study Design: This study employed a mixed-methods research approach. This method is well-suited for this research as it combines both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the experiences faced by mathematics students in integrating chatbots into their learning process.

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Place and Duration of Study: The study was conducted at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, Laoang, Northern Samar, during the school year 2024-2025.

Methodology: The researchers included Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) Mathematics students from the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, during the school year 2024–2025, who have actively used chatbots in their mathematics education. 30 Participants were selected through purposive sampling. Data collection involved semi-structured one-on-one interviews and survey questionnaires. Thematic analysis was applied to qualitative data from interviews, while descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) were used to analyze quantitative survey data on chatbot usage.

Results: Out of 30 mathematics students, Cici was reported as the most frequently used chatbot among mathematics students, followed by ChatGPT and Copilot. Other chatbots like Meta AI, Perplexity, and Math AI were also noted, with less usage reported for Gemini, Question AI, Gauth Math, Sizzling, and Quillbot. It also revealed that chatbots assisted students with problem-solving in mathematics, enhanced conceptual understanding, ensured accuracy and validity, expanded mathematical knowledge, improved accessibility and convenience, boosted student confidence and engagement, and provided a student-friendly and time-saving learning experience, issues like dependency on chatbots, subscriptions or paywall issues, lack of details or clarity, inaccurate or unreliable answers, and internet connectivity issues were commonly mentioned. In response, students recommended strategies such as cross-verification of answers, avoiding over-reliance on chatbots, using multiple chatbots, clarifying or specifying questions, improving access and free tools, responsible use, and student discipline.

Conclusion: Chatbots like Cici, ChatGPT, and Copilot play a growing role in mathematics education, aiding students in problem-solving and conceptual understanding. While they enhance accessibility and engagement, challenges such as dependency and accuracy concerns exist. Students advocate for responsible usage, cross-checking answers, and refining queries to ensure AI tools support independent learning rather than replace it.

Keywords: Chatbots; mathematics education; AI tools; student engagement; math learning; problem-solving skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

In an era where technology permeates every aspect of life, mathematics education stands at a crucial point, ready to transform innovative learning tools and processes. The advent of AI-powered tools and digital platforms presents a remarkable opportunity to make mathematics education more engaging, accessible, and effective, ensuring that every student, regardless of background, can develop a strong foundation in mathematics and apply it to real-world scenarios. Nowadays, technologies are revolutionizing how students learn mathematical concepts, leading to a greater emphasis on mathematics education. As stated by Egara and Mosimege (2024), mathematics is a subject that everyone must understand. It serves as a fundamental skill required in both education and daily life. Moreover, the primary reason for learning mathematics is the belief that it is useful in everyday life and can help achieve a better quality of life. Mathematics education is not simply about teaching numbers; it's about empowering individuals with the critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills necessary to thrive in a complex and ever-evolving world.

However, mathematics education faces challenges in effectively engaging students and fostering a deep understanding of complex concepts. Traditional teaching methods often fall short in engaging students and fostering a deep understanding of mathematical concepts. Over time, some mathematics researchers have pinpointed various factors contributing to this issue of underperformance among students in mathematics. These include insufficient foundational knowledge, ineffective teaching techniques that do not cater to diverse learning styles, and a lack of personalized support to accommodate varying learning paces and styles (Egara and Mosimege, 2024). A study on freshmen students at Adiong Memorial Polytechnic State College-Laboratory High School found that students face difficulties in learning mathematics. The primary issue identified was related to the instruction and teaching methodologies employed by their teachers. This inadequate teaching and learning approach hindered students' understanding and success in mathematics, highlighting a need for improvement in instructional strategies and learning tools (Radiamoda, 2024).

Technology has profoundly transformed the landscape of math education, offering innovative tools and resources that enhance student engagement, facilitate personalized learning, and promote accessibility that complements traditional teaching approaches. Technology provides the resources, facilities, and computing power required to create and implement artificial intelligence (AI) systems (Ahmad et al., 2022; Mikalef & Gupta, 2021). Various chatbots, developed using advanced AI technologies, represent the latest advancements in AI-driven educational tools. These chatbots offer personalized and interactive learning experiences, making them promising tools for enhancing mathematics education. Some notable examples of chatbots in mathematics education include Thinkster Math, which combines AI-driven tutoring with human support for a personalized math learning experience (Thinkster Math, 2024); Cognii, an AI-powered chatbot that delivers personalized feedback and assessment in subjects like writing and mathematics (Cognii, 2024); ALEKS, which provides adaptive learning in math, chemistry, and economics, tailoring personalized learning paths to fill knowledge gaps (ALEKS, 2025); Carnegie Learning's Mika, which offers real-time tutoring in mathematics and tracks student progress (Carnegie Learning, 2025); and IBM Watson Tutor, which leverages AI to provide personalized tutoring in subjects like math and science, offering individualized explanations, practice questions, and feedback (IBM Watson, 2025). The potential of these chatbots to improve education, solve mathematical problems, and enhance student learning is vast. For example, they can assist teachers and educators in generating personalized and relevant educational content for students (Guo et al., 2023). This can lead to an increase in student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement in mathematics education.

While chatbots offer impressive capabilities, they are not without limitations. Chatbots may occasionally produce responses that are irrelevant or inaccurate, especially in complex mathematical problems (Tenhundfeld & ChatGPT, 2023). They excel in probabilistic reasoning but can struggle with precise, rule-based calculations (Tenhundfeld & ChatGPT, 2023). Chatbots can have difficulty of fully understanding the context or nuances of certain topics, leading to potential misunderstandings or incorrect responses (Pardos & Bhandari, 2023). The effectiveness of chatbots heavily depends

on the quality and breadth of the data they were trained on. Inadequate or biased training data can result in suboptimal performance (Rahayu, 2024) of human teachers. Therefore, it is crucial to employ chatbots responsibly and ethically, ensuring that they are used to complement, not replace, human educators (Pardos & Bhandari, 2023; Rahayu, 2024).

To fill this research gap, this study aimed to explore the potential of chatbots in mathematics education by introducing them as an innovative learning tool for Bachelor of Secondary Education Math students. Specifically, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how chatbots can be integrated into the mathematics learning process. Ultimately, this study aims to enhance the knowledge and understanding of chatbots' capabilities and their impact on educational environments, thereby contributing to improved educational outcomes in mathematics. The findings from this study will offer valuable insights to mathematics teachers, academics, and policymakers, assisting them in making informed decisions about the utilization of chatbots in mathematics classrooms.

1.1 Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the potential of chatbots in mathematics education by introducing them as an innovative learning tool for Bachelor of Secondary Education Math students, the research questions were:

1. What specific chatbots are used in learning by mathematics students?
2. How does the integration of chatbots influence mathematics learning as assessed by mathematics students?
3. What challenges do mathematics students encounter when using chatbots?
4. What strategies can enhance the use of chatbots in learning mathematics?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study used a mixed-method research approach to examine the integration of chatbots in mathematics education as innovative learning tools. By combining quantitative methods—such as surveys and data analysis—with qualitative insights from interviews and observations, the research provided a comprehensive view of chatbot usage. The study aimed to explore the

specific chatbots students had used and assess their potential in enhancing mathematics learning. Through this approach, the research sought to present a well-rounded understanding of chatbots as educational tools.

2.2 Participants

This study examined BSED mathematics students at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, during the school year 2024-2025 who actively used chatbots in their learning process. Through purposive sampling, participants were selected to ensure diverse perspectives and experiences. These students were responsible for integrating chatbots into their studies, engaging directly with them as part of their educational practices.

2.3 Research Instrument

Researchers developed a survey questionnaire and interview guide to examine chatbot usage in mathematics learning. The survey gathered information on specific chatbots students had used, while the interviews explored their experiences, including benefits and challenges. To ensure reliability, an expert review by educators and researchers in mathematics education provided valuable feedback on the interview guide's content and structure. Additionally, a pilot test was administered to a small, representative sample of participants to identify any practical issues, such as question clarity and interview flow. Feedback from the pilot test was used to refine the interview guide.

2.4 Data Collection

The researchers collected data through survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Participants first completed a survey identifying the chatbots they had used, followed by one-on-one interviews to provide deeper insights into their experiences. The interview process began with an overview of the study's objectives, ensuring informed consent. Open-ended and specific questions explored the impact of chatbots on mathematics education, as well as the challenges students faced and potential solutions. With consent, interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes. The findings contributed to a deeper understanding of chatbots as innovative learning tools and provided a thorough analysis of students' experiences and perspectives

2.5 Data Analysis

This study utilized descriptive statistics to analyze quantitative data and thematic analysis to examine qualitative data from interviews on chatbot usage in mathematics education. Researchers transcribed and reviewed interview recordings, using open coding to identify key patterns, which were then refined into broader themes representing students' experiences. Themes were validated for accuracy, revised if overlapping, and clearly defined. Findings were interpreted based on research questions and objectives, with direct participant quotes included to illustrate insights. This approach provided a thorough examination of how chatbots functioned as innovative learning tools for mathematics students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Chatbots Used by the Students in Learning Mathematics

As shown in Fig. 1, based on the survey of 30 respondents regarding the specific chatbots they use in learning mathematics, the most commonly used chatbot is Cici, selected by 20 respondents (66.7%) and accounting for 23.5% of all chatbot mentions. ChatGPT follows closely, used by 14 respondents (46.7%), while Copilot was selected by 13 (43.3%). Other frequently mentioned chatbots include Meta AI (33.3%), Perplexity and Math AI (both at 20.0%), and Gemini (16.7%). Less commonly used chatbots include Question AI (13.3%), Gauth Math (10.0%), and both Sizzling and QuillBot, each mentioned by only 6.7% of respondents. These findings indicate that students utilize a diverse range of AI tools for learning mathematics, with a notable preference for Cici, ChatGPT, and Copilot.

The study highlights the growing role of AI-driven tools in mathematics education, with students showing a strong preference for chatbots like Cici and ChatGPT, aligning with research by Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) on AI's expanding influence in education. The widespread use of these chatbots suggests that students value accessibility, interactive engagement, and personalized support, key factors in mathematics learning, as noted by Holmes et al. (2023). Additionally, the diversity of chatbot usage demonstrates students' willingness to explore various platforms for academic success (Lim & Wang, 2023). However, the lower adoption of some chatbots may indicate functionality

Fig. 1. Chatbots used by students in learning mathematics

limitations or lower familiarity, as highlighted by Kim et al. (2021), underscoring the need for educators and developers to enhance accessibility and ensure AI-powered tools effectively support diverse learning needs.

3.2 Influence of Chatbots on Learning in Mathematics

Seven primary themes emerged from the participants' influence of chatbots on learning in mathematics: Assisted problem-solving in mathematics, enhanced conceptual understanding, ensured accuracy and validity, expanded mathematical knowledge, improved accessibility, and convenience, boosted student confidence and engagement, and Student-friendly and time-saving.

3.2.1 Assisted problem-solving in mathematics

Most of the participants turn to chatbots when they encounter difficulties in solving mathematical equations. They indicate that chatbots serve as an accessible source of information, helping them navigate challenging problems by providing examples, solutions, and explanations. Rather than being stuck on a problem, they rely on AI-powered assistance to guide them through the steps, making the process more manageable. This highlights that chatbots are transforming the way users

approach mathematical problem-solving by providing accessible guidance and step-by-step solutions, making learning more efficient and manageable.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"One of the reasons why I use these chatbots is because of the difficulties in answering mathematical equations."

"There are some problems in mathematics that I find difficult to answer. So I go to chatbots to ask for some information."

"If I have a difficulty in understanding the concept in mathematics, I ask chatbots to give an example or a solution."

"I go to chatbots to ask for some information for me to know what could be the process in answering that problem."

Research indicates that AI-powered chatbots play a crucial role in assisting students with mathematical problems. Studies highlight that chatbots provide immediate support, answering students' questions, offering explanations, and supplying additional resources (Labadze et al., 2023). Digital tools play a crucial role in modern mathematics education, supporting visualization, problem-solving, and knowledge enhancement (Cabugwason et al., 2024). Additionally, research has found that students recognize AI-powered chatbots as valuable tools for learning mathematics, particularly for delivering detailed

explanations and solutions (Gökçearsan et al., 2024). Furthermore, AI chatbots contribute to homework and study assistance, enabling a personalized learning experience that aids students in navigating challenging concepts (Antony & Ramnath, 2024).

3.2.2 Enhanced conceptual understanding

Participants express that chatbots help make abstract mathematical concepts clearer, particularly in subjects like calculus. They use chatbots to obtain explanations beyond their textbooks, gaining a more concrete understanding of topics they struggle with. The ability to ask for clarifications on specific concepts ensures they grasp the fundamental ideas needed for effective problem-solving. This suggests that chatbots enhance learning by providing deeper explanations and personalized clarifications, helping users better understand complex mathematical concepts beyond traditional resources.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

- "To clarify some information to make my understanding concrete."*
- "It greatly influences my understanding... especially in our subject calculus."*
- "I ask chatbots for clarifications on concepts I don't understand."*
- "Chatbots help me understand if I don't know the process of solving a particular problem."*
- "It gives me clarification on a specific topic that I don't understand."*

Research indicates that AI-powered chatbots help students gain a clearer understanding of abstract mathematical concepts. Research on pre-service mathematics teachers highlights a moderate level of conceptual understanding, with recurring errors across diverse mathematical topics, demonstrating the need for targeted interventions and adaptive learning strategies (Nobis, 2024). Chatbots provide detailed explanations and step-by-step solutions, assisting learners in clarifying difficult topics (Gökçearsan et al., 2024). Additionally, research has found that AI-powered tools support students in understanding problem-solving processes, ensuring they develop a strong conceptual foundation (Dahal et al., 2023). Furthermore, AI chatbots are recognized as valuable resources for learning mathematics, offering alternative explanations and personalized assistance to make complex concepts more accessible (Ergene & Caylan Ergene, 2024).

3.2.3 Ensured accuracy and validity

Participants highlight the importance of using chatbots to verify solutions. Whether checking if their answers are correct or ensuring they followed the right steps in solving a problem, chatbots function as a useful validation tool. Responses suggest that before using chatbots, students did not always double-check their solutions, but now, they confirm accuracy to improve their confidence in their answers. This suggests that chatbots play a crucial role in reinforcing accuracy and confidence in problem-solving, encouraging students to double-check their work and develop a more reliable approach to verifying mathematical solutions.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

- "I use chatbots to check if my solutions are correct."*
- "To make sure that the steps that I'm using for solving a particular problem are correct."*
- "I used these chatbots to check if my solutions are somewhat similar to those they provided."*
- "I just solve it and I no longer double-check my answers before, but now with chatbots, I make sure my solutions are correct."*

Studies highlight that AI chatbots enhance students' ability to verify mathematical solutions, providing structured guidance to validate their reasoning and ensure correctness in problem-solving (Ergene & Caylan Ergene, 2024). Some research emphasizes the importance of structured learning environments that enhance student engagement, time management, and technological proficiency. It highlights how digital tools, including AI-powered applications, contribute to improving students' ability to navigate complex academic challenges (Nobis, 2024). Additionally, research has found that AI-driven chatbots improve students' precision by offering comparative analysis, and reinforcing problem-solving strategies (Dahal et al., 2023). Furthermore, AI-powered tools are recognized for their ability to boost students' confidence in mathematical accuracy by enabling them to cross-check their solutions with AI-generated responses (Gökçearsan et al., 2024).

3.2.4 Expanded mathematical knowledge

Participants recognize chatbots as a valuable tool for expanding their mathematical knowledge. Instead of relying solely on personal understanding, they seek additional insights,

methods, and problem-solving approaches. The responses show that chatbots provide new perspectives, broadening students' ability to apply different strategies in answering mathematical problems. This highlights that chatbots contribute to a deeper and more flexible approach to learning mathematics, allowing students to explore diverse problem-solving strategies and gain broader insights beyond their initial understanding.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"I use chatbots to gain more knowledge about the answers."
"It helps me improve some of the methods or ways of solving specific problems."
"To have another form of answer—not just my knowledge—but to gain more knowledge."
"It broadens my understanding of a particular topic that I ask."

Research indicates that AI-powered chatbots contribute significantly to students' learning by offering diverse explanations and problem-solving strategies. Studies highlight that chatbots provide expanded methods for solving complex equations, allowing students to develop a more comprehensive understanding of mathematical concepts (Gökçearslan et al., 2024). Additionally, research has found that technology-driven tools, including math applications, play a crucial role in visualization, problem-solving, and knowledge enhancement, helping students develop a deeper conceptual understanding of mathematical principles (Cabugwason et al., 2024). Furthermore, AI chatbots are recognized as effective educational resources that enhance knowledge acquisition by delivering personalized and contextual explanations tailored to students' needs (Ergene & Caylan Ergene, 2024).

3.2.5 Improved accessibility and convenience

Participants appreciate the accessibility of chatbots, noting how easy they are to use compared to traditional methods such as books. The instant availability of chatbots allows students to learn at their own pace without relying on fixed schedules or limited resources. The convenience of obtaining information with just one click makes chatbots an adaptable and efficient learning tool. This suggests that chatbots enhance learning flexibility by providing instant access to information, allowing students

to study independently without time constraints or reliance on traditional resources.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"It becomes easier to access information, unlike using books."
"Chatbots are convenient enough to be used for students who are eager to learn."
"It's easy to use and very adaptable for students."
"One click only, they offer a lot of information."
"It becomes easier to access the information, unlike using books."
"One click or search, and you are given enough concepts."
"It is easy to access the information."
"I can easily access the process of solving the problem."

AI-powered chatbots enhance accessibility and convenience in education by providing instant access to information and personalized learning experiences. Findings reveal limited digital resources, resulting in infrequent use of educational software social media, and math apps (Nobis, 2021). Studies show that chatbots improve students' ability to learn at their own pace without relying on fixed schedules or limited resources (Labadze et al., 2023). Additionally, research indicates that AI-driven tools help students navigate educational content more efficiently by offering immediate responses and explanations tailored to their learning needs (Ergene & Ergene, 2024). Furthermore, studies have found that chatbots facilitate adaptability in learning by supporting diverse learning styles and increasing students' engagement in self-directed study (Pepin et al., 2025). With the convenience of obtaining information with just one click, AI chatbots continue to be a valuable and efficient tool for students in modern education.

3.2.6 Boosted student confidence and engagement

Responses indicate that chatbot-assisted learning contributes to students' confidence in mathematics. By gaining a better understanding and verifying their solutions, students feel more prepared to engage in discussions and participate in math-related activities. Chatbots encourage active learning, helping students become more assertive in conveying information and collaborating with peers. This suggests that

chatbot-assisted learning fosters greater confidence in mathematics by enabling students to verify their solutions, deepen their understanding, and actively participate in discussions, ultimately strengthening their ability to engage and collaborate with others.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"It makes me confident when it comes to delivering or conveying information to my classmates."

"It helps me to be active in our discussion."

"I become more confident in understanding and participating in math activities."

Research indicates that chatbot-assisted learning enhances students' confidence in mathematics by providing immediate feedback and interactive problem-solving experiences. Research indicates that finding effective ways to support and engage students is crucial (Lupas et al., 2024). Students using chatbots in online math learning platforms appreciated the real-time support and step-by-step explanations, which helped them feel more confident in solving problems independently (Cheng et al., 2024). AI chatbots offer detailed solutions and multiple approaches to mathematical reasoning, allowing students to verify their answers and gain a deeper understanding of concepts (Ergene & Caylan Ergene, 2025). Additionally, chatbots contribute to students' self-assurance by reinforcing their learning through personalized guidance and curriculum development (Sawyer, 2024).

3.2.7 Student-friendly and time-saving

Many participants express that chatbots are easy to use and efficient for learning. Unlike searching for answers in textbooks, chatbots present information in a summarized and digestible format, making studying more manageable. The flexibility to use chatbots at any time ensures that students can adapt their learning schedule according to their needs, optimizing their study time. This suggests that chatbots enhance learning efficiency by providing easily accessible, concise explanations, allowing students to streamline their study process and customize their learning schedule based on their individual needs.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"It is student-friendly and offers me time on when I will be using this chatbot."

"It becomes easier for students to learn because the information is summarized."

"It's easy to access and saves time compared to looking up information in textbooks."

Chatbots allow students to access educational content quickly and adapt their learning schedules to their needs. Students adopted strategies such as identifying free alternatives, enhancing app literacy, and seeking guidance from teachers or peers (Cabugwason et al., 2024). AI chatbots improve accessibility and motivation by offering concise explanations, reducing the time spent searching for information in textbooks (Gökçeşlan et al., 2024). Students perceive chatbots as effective digital learning tools, appreciating their ease of use and ability to provide instant responses (Vanichvasin, 2021). Additionally, students who recognize the advantages of chatbots show a strong intention to use them for academic purposes, emphasizing their efficiency and adaptability (Ayanwale & Molefi, 2024).

3.3 Challenges Encountered by Mathematics Students When Using Chatbots

There are multifaceted challenges faced by students when using chatbots, five themes emerged such as dependency on chatbots, subscriptions or paywall issues, lack of details or clarity, inaccurate or unreliable answers, and internet connectivity issues.

3.3.1 Dependency on chatbots

Participants expressed concerns about over-reliance on chatbots for completing assignments and solving problems. Instead of attempting solutions on their own first, they turn to AI tools for immediate answers, which can hinder their critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. While chatbots are valuable resources, excessive dependence may reduce students' ability to apply learned concepts independently, potentially impacting their long-term mathematical development. This suggests that while chatbots enhance accessibility and learning efficiency, over-reliance on them may weaken students' critical thinking and independent problem-solving skills, highlighting the need for balanced usage to support long-term mathematical growth.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"I've become dependent on chatbots for my assignments."

"I don't attempt to solve problems on my own before using chatbots."

"I rely too much on chatbots and it affects my critical thinking."

"Most students rely on these chatbots and become lazy."

"I go directly to chatbots without first solving on my own."

"I lose confidence in answering because I am too dependent on chatbots."

"I've become more dependent on chatbots for assignments."

Studies indicate that excessive dependence on chatbots may discourage independent learning and reduce students' ability to apply concepts effectively. Students who frequently rely on AI dialogue systems struggle with cognitive skills such as decision-making and analytical reasoning (Zhai et al., 2024). High school students who depend on chatbots for assignments exhibit lower creativity and problem-solving abilities (Kumar et al., 2024). Additionally, students who rely too much on AI-generated responses may experience decreased motivation and engagement in learning (Zhai et al., 2024). Findings suggest that chatbots should be viewed as supplementary tools rather than replacements for independent learning (Lupas et al., 2024).

3.3.2 Subscription or paywall issues

Participants note that some chatbot services require subscriptions or paid access to premium features. This financial barrier can limit accessibility, particularly for those who cannot afford additional costs. While free versions of chatbots offer basic functionality, students express frustration when key features—such as more advanced problem-solving tools or in-depth explanations—are restricted behind paywalls. This issue highlights the need for equitable access to AI-powered learning tools. This suggests that financial barriers to premium chatbot features may create disparities in access to advanced learning tools, emphasizing the importance of making AI-powered education more inclusive and widely available.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"Some features of chatbots require subscriptions."

"Some applications I used required a subscription to access the best features."

"Certain chatbots limit access unless you pay for the full version."

Research highlights concerns about the financial barriers associated with AI chatbots, particularly regarding subscription-based access to premium features. Findings reveal limited digital resources, resulting in infrequent use of educational software social media, and math apps (Nobis, 2021). Studies indicate that while free versions of chatbots provide basic functionality, students often express frustration when advanced tools are restricted behind paywalls. Students in higher education perceive AI chatbots as useful but are concerned about the cost of accessing premium features, which may limit equitable learning opportunities (Schei et al., 2024). Additionally, subscription-based AI tools impact students' engagement, with many opting for free alternatives despite their limitations (Monrad et al., 2024).

3.3.3 Lack of details or clarity

Some participants struggle with vague or overly broad explanations from chatbots. While AI-powered tools aim to simplify concepts, responses can sometimes lack specificity, making it difficult for students to understand certain mathematical principles, symbols, or formulas. Additionally, missing steps in problem-solving processes can create confusion, requiring students to seek further clarification from other sources, such as teachers or textbooks. This suggests that while chatbots enhance accessibility to learning, unclear or incomplete explanations can hinder understanding, emphasizing the need for more precise responses and complementary guidance from educators or other reliable sources.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"Sometimes chatbots give broad solutions that I cannot understand."

"The answers from chatbots are too vague and not specific enough."

"The explanations are difficult to understand, especially the symbols used."

"The symbols they use are hard to understand."

"The illustrations in the formulas are sometimes difficult to comprehend."

"Chatbots sometimes use terminology that is unfamiliar to me."

“The answers lack detail and some steps in solving a problem are missing.”

Research highlights concerns about vague or overly broad explanations provided by AI chatbots, particularly in mathematical subjects. Findings indicate that math applications help concept development, through usability barriers can affect implementations (Cabugwason et al., 2024). Studies indicate that while chatbots aim to simplify concepts, their responses may sometimes lack specificity, leading to confusion. Students often struggle with chatbot explanations due to their generalized nature, making it difficult to grasp specific mathematical principles (Antony & Ramnath, 2024). Students perceive AI chatbots as useful but sometimes frustrating when responses are too vague or do not align with traditional teaching methods (Schei et al, 2024).

3.3.4 Inaccurate or unreliable answers

Participants report instances where chatbots provide incorrect or inconsistent solutions. Some responses differ from what teachers have taught, leading to misunderstandings and uncertainty. Additionally, chatbots may generate solutions that are irrelevant to the problem or include unnecessary information, causing frustration. This reinforces the importance of verifying chatbot-generated responses and cross-referencing them with reliable sources. This suggests that while chatbots offer valuable learning support, inaccuracies or inconsistencies in their responses can create confusion, emphasizing the need for students to verify solutions and cross-reference information with trusted sources like teachers and textbooks.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

“Sometimes the solution is not right.”

“Chatbots offer solutions that do not apply to the problem.”

“I received inaccurate or unclear answers from chatbots.”

“The answers are sometimes different from what the teacher discussed.”

“Sometimes, the chatbots offer unnecessary solutions that are not related to the problem.”

Studies indicate that chatbot-generated answers may sometimes differ from traditional teaching methods, leading to misunderstandings. Research highlights the importance of enhanced instructional strategies and targeted interventions

to improve students’ problem-solving skills in mathematics (Adoro et al., 2024). Students who rely on AI dialogue systems often encounter discrepancies between chatbot-generated solutions and classroom instruction, affecting their comprehension (Zhai et al., 2024). Chatbots in education may produce misleading or irrelevant responses, reinforcing the importance of critical evaluation (Kooli, 2023). AI-generated answers may lack authenticity and coherence, requiring students to verify the information before relying on it (Elkhatat, 2023).

3.3.5 Internet connectivity issues

Since chatbots require an internet connection to function, students face challenges when experiencing poor connectivity or lack of access to data. Slow response times and difficulties retrieving information are common complaints, especially in areas with unstable internet service. This limitation underscores the importance of ensuring reliable digital infrastructure to support AI-driven learning experiences. This indicates that unreliable internet connectivity can hinder their effectiveness, highlighting the need for improved digital infrastructure to ensure consistent and efficient AI-powered education.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

“One of the challenges is the internet connection because not all the time the internet connection is strong.”

“I encountered challenges with low internet connections.”

“It takes time for them to respond if the internet is slow.”

“If you don’t have data, you cannot access the information you want.”

“Chatbots require data to function, and without it, they cannot provide answers.”

“One of the disadvantages is the internet connection.”

“When I don’t have internet or load, I can’t use the chatbots.”

“It requires internet, and if the connection is poor, I can’t use it.”

Research highlights concerns about internet connectivity and technical issues as significant barriers to chatbot-assisted learning, particularly for students in areas with unstable access. Findings reveal that limited digital resources result in infrequent use of educational software, social media, and mathematics applications (Nobis, 2021). Math apps support concept

development and problem-solving, however, restricted internet access could hinder effective usage (Cabugwason et al., 2024). Studies indicate that reliance on digital infrastructure can limit students' ability to seek help when needed. Students often struggle with AI chatbot accessibility due to poor internet connections, affecting their ability to engage in learning activities (Gökçearslan et al., 2024). Technical issues, such as slow response times and data limitations, can disrupt students' learning experiences and reduce their trust in AI-based educational tools (Davar et al, 2025).

3.4 Proposed Solutions and Strategies to Enhance the Use of Chatbots in Learning Mathematics

The participants offered several recommendations to enhance the use of chatbots in learning mathematics. These recommendations fell into six categories: Cross-verification of answers, avoiding over-reliance on chatbots, using multiple chatbots, clarifying or specifying questions, improving access and free tools, responsible use, and student discipline.

3.4.1 Cross-verification of answers

Participants recognize that while chatbots provide solutions, it is essential to verify their accuracy. Many prefer to cross-check information with textbooks, teachers, or other reliable sources to ensure correctness. This practice helps prevent reliance on potentially incorrect AI-generated responses and promotes critical thinking by encouraging students to evaluate different sources before accepting an answer. This suggests that verifying their accuracy is crucial. Cross-checking with reliable sources helps prevent misinformation and fosters critical thinking, ensuring that students develop a well-rounded understanding of mathematical concepts.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

- "I recheck it for my own."*
- "I still look for different sources like books and reliable sources."*
- "I ask teachers to verify the answers from chatbots."*

Studies indicate that while chatbots provide solutions, verifying their accuracy through textbooks, teachers, or other reliable sources is essential. Research highlights the importance of

enhanced instructional strategies and targeted interventions to improve students' problem-solving skills in mathematics (Adoro et al., 2024). Students use multiple sources to validate AI-generated responses, ensuring correctness and reducing reliance on potentially inaccurate information (Elkhatat, 2023). Students in higher education actively cross-check chatbot-generated answers to maintain academic integrity and improve learning outcomes (Schei et al., 2024). Additionally, AI chatbots can enhance learning but require transparency and validation mechanisms to support student comprehension (Salminen et al., 2024).

3.4.2 Avoiding over-reliance on chatbots

Some participants acknowledge the importance of using chatbots wisely. They emphasize that while chatbots can serve as a helpful guide, they should not replace personal effort and independent problem-solving. By attempting to solve problems first and using chatbots only as a supplementary tool, students can maintain their analytical skills and strengthen their mathematical reasoning. This implies that responsible use of chatbots is essential for maintaining strong problem-solving skills. While chatbots provide valuable support, relying on personal effort first ensures that students develop their analytical abilities and deepen their mathematical understanding.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

- "Don't be too dependent."*
- "Answer it first on your own."*
- "We can use these chatbots as a guide."*

Studies indicate that while chatbots can serve as valuable learning aids, excessive dependence may hinder independent thinking. Students who frequently rely on AI dialogue systems struggle with cognitive skills such as decision-making and analytical reasoning (Zhai et al., 2024). High school students recognize the benefits of AI chatbots but emphasize the importance of using them as supplementary tools rather than primary sources of learning (Lee & Maeng, 2023). Additionally, students who attempt to solve problems independently before consulting chatbots demonstrate stronger mathematical reasoning and creativity (Kumar et al., 2024). Furthermore research underscores the need for chatbot interventions that support rather than replace cognitive skill development (Nobis, 2025).

3.4.3 Using multiple chatbots

To improve the accuracy of solutions, participants suggest consulting multiple AI chatbots instead of relying on just one. Different chatbots may generate varying responses, and by comparing outputs, students can determine the most reliable and well-explained answer. This strategy ensures a broader understanding of mathematical concepts and reduces errors in problem-solving. This suggests that comparing multiple AI chatbots allows students to identify the most accurate and well-explained solutions, promoting a more thorough understanding of mathematical concepts while minimizing errors in problem-solving.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

*"I go to Copilot if I'm not contented with Perplexity."
"Use a variety of chatbots to find the most accurate answers."*

Studies indicate that different chatbots may generate varying responses, and comparing outputs allows students to determine the most reliable and well-explained answer. Students in higher education actively use multiple AI chatbots to cross-check information, ensuring a broader understanding of complex concepts (Schei et al., 2024). Students leverage AI chatbot diversity to refine their problem-solving strategies and reduce errors in mathematical reasoning (Jo, 2024). Furthermore, research explores the role of digital learning environments emphasizing the need for reliable evaluation mechanisms to ensure the effectiveness of chatbots as educational tools (Nobis, 2023).

3.4.4 Clarifying or specifying questions

Participants understand that chatbots may provide unclear or broad answers when questions are vague. To address this, they suggest refining queries by chunking complex problems into smaller parts or specifying precise keywords. A well-structured question leads to more relevant and comprehensive responses, allowing students to obtain clearer explanations from AI tools. This implies that refining queries helps improve chatbot responses, ensuring that students receive more precise and comprehensive explanations by breaking down complex problems and using specific keywords.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

*"I chunk the questions and make it more specific."
"Specify the words in your questions to get clearer answers."*

Research highlights the importance of clarifying or specifying questions when interacting with AI chatbots to improve response accuracy. Studies indicate that refining queries by breaking complex problems into smaller parts or using precise keywords leads to more relevant and comprehensive answers. Research explores conceptual knowledge gaps in mathematics instruction, identifying areas where chatbots must be refined to improve accuracy and clarity (Nobis, 2025). Students who structure their questions effectively receive clearer explanations and more useful responses from AI chatbots (Peyton et al., 2025). Students benefit from chatbot-assisted learning when they provide well-defined queries, reducing confusion and improving comprehension (Vanichvasin, 2021). Additionally, AI chatbots in education can enhance learning outcomes when students refine their questions to align with chatbot processing capabilities (Labadze et al., 2023).

3.4.5 Improving access and free tools

Subscription-based chatbots may limit access for some students, so they opt for free AI tools that provide similar functionalities without financial constraints. Some students prefer using chatbots that operate without an internet connection or consume minimal data, ensuring accessibility even in areas with limited connectivity. These findings highlight the need for more accessible, cost-effective chatbot options to ensure equitable learning opportunities for all.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

*"We use chatbots that don't require subscriptions."
"I use Meta AI through Messenger because it didn't require data."*

Research highlights the importance of improving access to AI chatbots and free tools, particularly for students facing financial constraints or limited internet connectivity. Studies indicate that subscription-based chatbots may restrict accessibility, leading students to seek free alternatives with similar functionalities. Findings reveal that limited digital resources result in

infrequent use of educational software, social media, and mathematics applications (Nobis, 2021). Students benefit from free AI-powered learning tools, emphasizing their role in enhancing research knowledge without financial barriers (Vanichvasin, 2021). Affordable AI chatbots are gaining popularity among students, but financial constraints still pose challenges for widespread adoption (Gökçearslan et al., 2024). Additionally, students' mindset toward AI chatbot adoption is influenced by accessibility, with many preferring tools that require minimal data or function offline (Rahman et al., 2025).

3.4.6 Responsible use and student discipline

Participants acknowledge the importance of using chatbots responsibly. They emphasize the need to verify information before copying answers directly, promoting ethical academic practices. Being mindful of how AI-generated solutions are used encourages students to engage in meaningful learning instead of relying on chatbots as a shortcut for completing assignments. This implies that responsible use of chatbots fosters ethical academic practices, ensuring that students verify information and engage in meaningful learning rather than using chatbots as a shortcut for completing assignments.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

“Be a responsible user.”

“Always verify before copying the answers.”

“It depends on the students if they are responsible users of chatbots.”

Research highlights the importance of responsible use and student discipline when engaging with AI chatbots, emphasizing ethical academic practices. Studies indicate that verifying chatbot-generated information before copying answers directly helps students develop critical thinking and integrity in learning. Students in higher education recognize the need for responsible AI usage, ensuring that chatbots serve as learning aids rather than shortcuts for assignments (Schei et al., 2024). High school students acknowledge ethical concerns related to AI chatbots, emphasizing the importance of verifying responses and avoiding plagiarism (Lee & Maeng, 2023). Additionally, students who actively cross-check chatbot-generated answers demonstrate stronger academic discipline and engagement in learning (Kumar et al., 2024). Furthermore, research explores the role of digital

learning environments emphasizing the need for reliable evaluation mechanisms to ensure the effectiveness of chatbots as educational tools (Nobis, 2023).

4. CONCLUSION

The findings from this study highlight the significant and multifaceted role that chatbots play in the learning of mathematics among students. The survey results indicate that students rely on a variety of AI chatbots for learning mathematics, with Cici, ChatGPT, and Copilot being the most preferred choices. The prominence of certain chatbots highlights their effectiveness, and the presence of multiple AI tools reflects students' willingness to explore different platforms to optimize their learning. These findings underscore the growing role of AI in education and the importance of ensuring that chatbot technologies continue to support meaningful mathematical development.

Chatbots have a significant influence on mathematics learning, assisting problem-solving, enhancing conceptual understanding, ensuring accuracy and validity, expanding mathematical knowledge, improving accessibility and convenience, boosting student confidence and engagement, and providing a student-friendly and time-saving experience.

Despite these benefits, students were also aware of the limitations and challenges associated with chatbot use. Many students expressed concerns about dependency on chatbots, noting that excessive reliance could hinder their ability to think critically or solve problems independently. Subscription or paywall issues posed another challenge, creating disparities between those who could afford premium features and those with limited access to more accurate and detailed responses. Additionally, students struggled with the lack of details or clarity in chatbot explanations, which sometimes led to misunderstandings or incomplete learning. Inaccurate or unreliable answers further complicated problem-solving, as incorrect responses could mislead students rather than support their learning. Lastly, internet connectivity issues affected chatbot accessibility, limiting students' ability to seek AI-powered assistance when needed.

To optimize chatbot use in mathematics learning, students proposed six key strategies: cross-verifying answers for accuracy, avoiding over-

reliance, using multiple chatbots for varied explanations, refining questions for clearer responses, improving access to free tools, and fostering responsible usage with student discipline. These approaches ensure that chatbots supplement rather than replace independent problem-solving, promoting critical thinking while enhancing mathematical comprehension. However, educators and learners alike must remain mindful of their limitations and ensure that technology complements rather than replaces foundational learning practices.

CONSENT AND ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study prioritized ethical research practices to ensure data accuracy, reliability, and integrity. Researchers obtained approvals from key authorities, including the professor, thesis adviser, and the head of the BSED program, before proceeding. Informed consent was secured, ensuring participants understood the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw without penalty. Ethical principles of consent, anonymity, and confidentiality were strictly followed. After completing the study and data analysis, all audio/video recordings were permanently deleted using secure disposal methods to prevent unauthorized access or retrieval.

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Author(s) hereby declare that generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models, etc. have been used during the writing or editing of manuscripts. This explanation will include the name, version, model, and source of the generative AI technology and as well as all input prompts provided to the generative AI technology.

Details of the AI usage are given below:

This research utilized ChatGPT, CiCi, and copilot—advanced AI language models—for paraphrasing paragraphs and checking grammatical errors. The free ChatGPT app, along with Cici and Copilot, was employed as a tool to enhance the clarity and readability of the text, ensuring that ideas were effectively communicated while maintaining the original meaning. The use of these AI models contributed to refining the language and structure of the manuscript.

1. Used ChatGPT, CiCi, and copilot for paraphrasing paragraphs to improve the clarity and readability of the text.
2. Used ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot for checking language and grammar to enhance overall accuracy and fluency.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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